

Impact of Synthetic Bias on Estimates of State-Level 2010 Census Coverage Error¹

Timothy Kennel¹, Scott Konicki¹, Krista Heim¹

¹U.S. Census Bureau, 4600 Silver Hill Road, Washington, DC 20233

Abstract

To provide information about the coverage of the U.S. decennial census, the U.S. Census Bureau has estimated the population size in each state and the District of Columbia using dual-system estimation since 1980. A small-area estimation technique, called synthetic estimation, was used to estimate state- and county-level coverage errors for the 2010 Census. Regression models were fit at the national level and then used to predict census coverage for states and counties. This resulted in model or synthetic bias because people in some states had different coverage propensities than people in other states with similar characteristics. This synthetic bias was estimated and reported as part of the root mean squared error in 2010. For the 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey, coverage models included state-specific covariates, eliminating synthetic bias in the state coverage estimates. In this paper, we compare census coverage estimates and their associated measures of uncertainty under the 2010 and 2020 approaches to show how the inclusion of state covariates impacted coverage measurements and statistical tests.

Key Words: Dual-system estimation, Coverage error, Small-area estimation, Census

1. Introduction

Since 1980, the U.S. Census Bureau has compared decennial census counts to independent estimates of the population size to gauge the coverage error of the census using a post-enumeration survey (PES). The state-level coverage estimates published after the 2020 Census looked different from previous decades. Notably, the spread of the state-level coverage estimates was greater than seen in prior decades and mean squared errors were larger.

After the 2010 Census, the Census Bureau reported that no state² had a statistically significant undercount or overcount of people. In leading up to the release of estimates of net coverage error for the 2020 Census, the U.S. Census Bureau improved the way it estimated net coverage error. Specifically, efforts were made to eliminate synthetic bias in state-level estimates of census coverage error. This was accomplished by adding state fixed effects in the coverage models. As a result, the Census Bureau was better able to detect coverage errors in 2020, estimating that the 2020 Census counts were less than the population estimates in six states and more than the population estimates in eight states. There could be many factors contributing to the differences between 2010 and 2020. One notable factor impacting the coverage estimates is that synthetic bias was reduced in 2020 state-level coverage estimates through inclusion of a state effect in coverage models.

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² For this paper, we treat the District of Columbia (DC) as the statistical equivalent of a state and refer to DC as a state.

To better understand how this change in estimation impacted comparisons of coverage estimates between 2010 and 2020, this paper compares synthetic and direct estimates of 2010 Census percent net coverage error. The focus is on how synthetic bias impacted point estimates, estimates of mean squared error, and tests of statistical significance for estimates of percent net coverage error.

2. Background

2.1 Post-Enumeration Survey

The Census Bureau has a long history of conducting post-enumeration surveys to estimate the coverage of the decennial census. Coverage error for a census refers to the difference between the census count and a benchmark of the true population. In the U.S., a post-enumeration survey provides one independent estimate of the population size. The survey uses on a technique called dual-system estimation or capture-recapture estimation. The post-enumeration survey conducts an enumeration of people and housing units independently of the Census in sample areas. The independent sample is matched to the census and the size of the population is estimated. The Census Bureau has been using post-enumeration surveys to assess the census counts since 1950 and to calculate dual-system estimates of the population size since 1980.

The 2010 post-enumeration survey began with a planned sample size of 300,000 housing units, the same size as the 2000 post-enumeration survey. In late 2009, the sample size was reduced to 170,000 housing units, the same size as the 1990 PES (Whitford 2009). The resources saved from the sample reduction were to be redirected toward an initiative to reduce the nonsampling error of the 2010 post-enumeration survey program via additional training and quality assurance activities.

Results from the 2010 post-enumeration survey were released in May 2012 (Mule 2012). The results included net coverage error estimates for the 50 states and the District of Columbia (DC) as well as counties and places with census populations of at least 100,000 people. These sub-national estimates were synthetic estimates because the dual-system estimation models did not include main effects for these entities.

In both 2010 and 2020, the dual-system estimator for people took the form³

$$\widehat{DSE} = \sum_{j \in K} \hat{\pi}_{dd,j} \frac{\hat{\pi}_{ce,j}}{\hat{\pi}_{m,j}}$$

where

- j is the census enumeration in domain K .
- $\hat{\pi}_{dd,j}$ is the predicted probability that the census enumeration is data-defined.
- $\hat{\pi}_{ce,j}$ is the predicted probability that the census enumeration is a correct enumeration.
- $\hat{\pi}_{m,j}$ is the predicted probability that the census enumeration is a match.

The probabilities were predicted from national survey-weighted logistic regression models. Thus, the dual-system estimates were dependent on models and could be subject to substantial synthetic bias. In 2010, the coverage models used to predict $\hat{\pi}_{dd,j}$, $\hat{\pi}_{ce,j}$, and $\hat{\pi}_{m,j}$ did not include state indicators. So, when K was a specific state, predictions were made using national trends, rather than state-specific trends.

To account for synthetic bias in these subnational estimates, the 2010 post-enumeration survey estimated the synthetic bias of state, county, and place estimates and included the bias when reporting root mean squared errors. These root mean squared errors were large enough such that no

³ Although not included here, some dual-system estimates in 2010 and 2020 included a term to better align them to sex ratios from the Demographic Analysis program. The details of this adjustment are beyond the scope of this paper and not relevant to the analysis presented in this paper.

statistically significant coverage errors were detected at the state, county, and place levels for person estimation in 2010. The 2020 PES reduced the synthetic bias in the net coverage estimates for states through enhancements to the modeling (Hill et al. 2022). Only sampling errors were reported for the 2020 PES.

Figure 1: Percent Net Coverage Error Estimates of Census by State from the PES, 1990 to 2020

Figure 1 shows the percent net coverage error for states from 1990 to 2020. The y-axis shows the percent net coverage error. Census net coverage error is the difference between the census counts and our estimate of the actual population size.

$$\text{Estimated percent net coverage error} = \frac{(\text{Census total} - \widehat{DSE})}{\widehat{DSE}} \times 100$$

A point below the black 0 line indicates an undercount, meaning the census count was below the state population estimate. A point above the 0 line indicates an overcount, meaning the census count was larger than the dual-system estimate of the state population. The x-axis shows the years of the past four decennial censuses in the U.S. Each line depicts a state. So, this graph shows how the percent net coverage error of the census changed for each of the 50 states and DC from 1990 to 2020. Because the percent net coverage error is estimated, the lines are measured with error. Some of the estimates are statistically significantly different from zero, but others are not.

The color of each line is based on the percent net coverage error in 1990. The colors follow the rainbow. This rainbow ordering is also seen in 2000, meaning that the relative position of the percent net coverage error was largely similar between 1990 and 2000. As we move to 2010 and 2020, the relative order changes. States that had high undercounts in 1990 don't seem to have high undercounts in 2020. We wouldn't necessarily expect a state that was undercounted in one census to also be undercounted in another census, but it is interesting to see the strong consistency between 1990 and 2000.

The most striking thing about this graph is that the estimates of percent net coverage error are spread out much more in 2020 than 2010. There are a lot of possible explanations. The 2020 Census was conducted during a pandemic. Additionally, census operations changed between 2010 and 2020. The 2020 Post-Enumeration Survey also had higher unit and item nonresponse than previous post-enumeration surveys. Another big change is that the models used to produce the dual-system estimates included state-specific effects – thereby eliminating synthetic bias. In 1990, 2000, and 2010, the state-level net coverage error estimates were driven by national and regional trends through a synthetic estimator. The synthetic estimation reduced sampling error, but such estimates were biased.

2.2 Synthetic Error

Estimates of census net coverage error from the U.S. Census Bureau's Post-Enumeration Survey have been used as an example of synthetic estimation in textbooks (Rao and Molina, 2015). It is well known that synthetic estimates can differ from the true population value because of sampling error and synthetic bias, while survey-weighted direct estimates can differ from true population values because of sampling error. The synthetic estimation of net coverage error has also been the subject of controversy, especially leading up to Census 2000, when early plans were to adjust census counts to small-area synthetic population estimates from the Post-Enumeration Survey.

After the 1990 Census, much of the debate on whether to adjust the census counts using the PES centered on the topic of synthetic estimation. Experts argued either side of the debate. For example, Mulry and Spencer (1993) presented evidence in favor of adjustment and synthetic estimation while Freedman and Wachter (1994) argued against adjustment noting the potential for high synthetic bias. Ultimately, synthetic bias was provided as a reason for not adjusting the 2000 Census for the purpose of the intercensal population estimates (U.S. Census Bureau 2003).

According to J.N.K Rao's textbook on small-area estimation, "an estimator is called a synthetic estimator if a reliable direct estimator for a larger area, covering several small areas, is used to derive an indirect estimator for a small area under the assumption that the small areas have the same characteristics as the large area." Rao credits parts of this definition to Maria Gonzalez's 1973 paper titled "Use and Evaluation of Synthetic Estimates."

In essence, the synthetic assumption for the post-enumeration survey was that national coverage trends for demographic groups were constant across lower levels of geography. Synthetic estimators 'borrow strength' from model parameters calculated using the national sample that were then applied to domains and small areas lacking sufficient sample size to estimate each parameter. This meant that the coverage rate for a small area was determined by the demographic characteristics of the people in that area rather than the coverage rates of people in the small area. That is, the coverage rate of the small area was largely driven by factors outside the area itself.

For a detailed technical description of synthetic estimation, refer to Zamora (2023). In essence, the 2010 PES synthetic estimator grouped the sample by several characteristics such as race, Hispanic origin, age, sex, tenure, and high-level geographic categories like census region. All people who shared the model set of covariates were assumed to have the same coverage rate, regardless of any differences the people may have in other characteristics that were not accounted for in the estimation. The synthetic assumption was that all people with the same combination of the covariates used in the estimation models had the same coverage rates.

Synthetic estimates depended on the model specified. For example, if African Americans and renters were undercounted on average across the U.S. then a model with race and tenure (owner or renter) would suggest that DC would be undercounted because it had a relatively high proportion of two nationally undercounted groups – African Americans and renters. However, renters and African Americans in DC might behave differently than the average in the U.S. After all, many renters and African Americans in DC work for the U.S. federal government. Additionally, DC has some of the highest rental costs in the U.S., making DC unique. So, there could be reason to suggest that renters and African Americans in DC might not fit the national trends. Models that include terms for education, employment, and cost of living might yield a very different coverage estimate for DC; but these additional variables were not collected in the census and not available for the coverage models.

Synthetic bias, then, is the difference, if any, in a domain's expected population estimate one would obtain by applying the synthetic estimator from a model fit on the true population versus simply tabulating over the true population (if it were known). To reduce the synthetic bias in the PES estimates, many variables are included in the estimation models.

Synthetic estimates can suffer from considerable bias for small areas. Yet synthetic estimates can have lower mean squared error than survey-weighted direct estimates. Even though synthetic estimates are biased, the variance is often lower than the sampling variance of direct estimates because the synthetic estimates are fit using the big national sample. If the synthetic bias is small or the small-area sample size is very small, the synthetic estimator can have lower mean squared error than a direct estimate.

Prior to the 2020 PES, state-level net coverage error estimates were subject to synthetic bias. For the 2020 PES, the estimation models included main effects for all estimation domains, including state, which removed synthetic bias. Specifically, the survey-weighted logistic regression coverage models were fit by solving estimating equations

$$\sum_{i \in s} d_i [y_i - \hat{\mu}(x_i)] = \mathbf{0}$$

where d_i is the design weight and $\hat{\mu}(x_i)$ is the modeled prediction based on a vector of covariates, x_i . Since x_i included an indicator for each state, the estimation procedure forced the weighted predictions for each state to equal the survey-weighted estimates for each state. Firth and Bennett (1998) call predictions estimated from such estimating equations internally bias calibrated (IBC). Adding state indicators into the model increased the variance of the modeled values because 50 (one of the 51 state equivalents was the reference group and no coefficient was estimated for it) additional coefficients had to be estimated; however, it eliminated the synthetic bias.

In this paper, we distinguish between the two estimators by calling the 2010 estimators without state effects “synthetic estimators” and the 2020 estimators with state effects “IBC model estimators.” In the process of estimating synthetic bias for the 2010 percent net coverage errors, survey-weighted direct estimates were also computed. Those state-level survey-weighted direct estimates only use sample within each state and do not have any synthetic bias. They are referred to as “direct estimates.”

3. Methodology

To explore how sensitive the estimates of state-level net coverage error in 2010 were to synthetic estimation, we calculated direct state-level estimates of net coverage error and their sampling errors from the 2010 data. Although not reported, survey-weighted direct estimates of net coverage error and their standard errors were computed in 2010 as part of the process to estimate the root mean squared errors of the published synthetic estimates.

Direct dual-system estimates were calculated for each state only using the data collected in each state. A limited set of post-strata were used to control heterogeneity bias. If sample sizes allowed, post-strata were formed by stratifying the sample in each state by cross-classifying minority status (minority, non-minority), tenure (owner, non-owner), and relationship type (member of the nuclear family, adult child of the householder, other members of the household). Small strata were collapsed with similar strata within each state to assure that each stratum had at least 100 cases. Within each stratum, dual-system estimates were created and added together to create a state-level dual-system estimate. Standard errors were calculated using the delete-a-group jackknife.

The Smoothed-Group Method was then used to reduce the variability of the direct state-level estimates. These direct dual-system estimates were treated as unbiased and compared to the synthetic state-level dual-system estimates. However, because the direct dual-system estimates were rather noisy, the estimated bias resulting from subtracting the synthetic and direct estimates was modeled using the Smoothed-Group Method. Specifically, five or six states were grouped together based on size. A Bayesian approach was then used to estimate the synthetic bias of the state-level estimates. These estimates of synthetic bias were squared and then added to estimates of synthetic variance to produce mean squared errors.

3.1 Survey-Weighted Direct Point Estimates

To explore how the 2010 estimates of state-level percent net coverage error differed from direct estimates, we extracted the post-stratified direct dual-system estimates used in the calculation of mean squared errors. However, since the direct state-level estimates and synthetic bias were estimated prior to the correlation bias adjustment, we computed a state-specific correlation bias adjustment for the direct state-level estimates so they could be compared to the reported synthetic estimates which included a correlation bias adjustment.

The production correlation bias adjustment used national estimates from Demographic Analysis by age group, sex, and race group to inflate some of the synthetic dual-system estimates. For more information on the correlation bias adjustment, see Konicki (2012). To shift the direct state-level estimates for correlation bias, we calculated the correlation bias effect on the synthetic estimates for each state and shifted the direct estimates by the same amount. Specifically, we first subtracted the published synthetic estimate for each state from the synthetic estimate prior to the correlation bias adjustment. The difference was then used to shift the direct estimate up or down. After this shift, the new direct dual-system estimates were compared to the 2010 census counts to create direct state-specific estimates of percent net coverage error. Such estimates were compared to the published synthetic estimates of percent net coverage error in 2010.

3.2 Synthetic Bias

In 2010, synthetic bias was estimated and included in reported estimates of root mean squared error. However, after calculating the root mean squared errors, the estimates of synthetic bias were archived and not readily available for this study. Fortunately, the estimated synthetic variance and root mean squared errors were available. So, instead of using the estimates of synthetic bias computed in 2010, we computed the squared synthetic bias by subtracting the synthetic variance from the published mean squared error.

3.3 Statistical Tests

To investigate how the estimation method impacted our ability to detect which states had statistically significant net coverage errors, we performed statistical tests using the direct estimates and also the synthetic estimates. For the direct estimates, we used the state-level direct estimates with the correlation bias shifting as the point estimate and the standard error of state-level direct estimates to form 90% confidence intervals of the state-level percent net coverage error. We assumed normality to form the confidence intervals. For the synthetic estimates, we used the reported state-level synthetic estimates and their root mean squared errors to form 90% confidence intervals of the state-level percent net coverage error.

4. Results

4.1 Point Estimates

Figure 1 plots the percent net coverage error estimate for each state for the 1990 to 2020 censuses. Each year contains 51 points (50 states and DC). For this discussion, what is important is not the point estimate for any particular state in a year, but rather the patterns of the states across the years. The 1990 and 2000 post-enumeration surveys each used post-stratification to estimate net coverage. These post-stratifications did not use state as a factor, and thus the state estimates were subject to synthetic bias. The national net coverage error estimates for the 1990 and 2000 censuses were -1.61 percent and 0.49 percent, respectively. We see that the states generally followed this positive shift from 1990 to 2000. Many state estimates appear to have moved by the same magnitude so that the ordering of states by their net coverage error was relatively constant for these years. There are two reasons for this. First, because neither 1990 nor 2000 post-stratification included state effects in the estimation, the estimates did not capture state-specific variation. The state estimates were synthetic and were clustered around the national rate. Secondly, states had different coverage estimates because the demographic makeup of the states differed, and these demographic characteristics were used in the post-stratification. However, the demographic makeup of most states did not change much between the years. Further the patterns of national-level net coverage error with respect to the

variables defining our post-strata (e.g., race, Hispanic origin, tenure, age group) were relatively constant across years (e.g., renters had higher undercounts than owners in each census). Thus, the estimates for most states were the same for both years aside from the overall shift in the national-level coverage rate.

Considering changes from 2000 to 2010, it appears that there was a large group of states that continued to move in parallel, with a small downward shift reflecting the estimated national-level coverage change from 0.49 in 2000 to 0.01 percent in 2010. However, there were some states that seemed to break away from the pattern of the previous decades. This may be because of the change from post-stratification to logistic regression modeling for the 2010 estimation. The 2010 logistic regression models did not include state effects, so the state estimates were still synthetic estimates. However, the regression approach allowed for more covariates and for continuous covariates. The 2010 models included a continuous covariate for the tract-level participation rate whereas the 1990 and 2000 post-stratifications used a binary (i.e., high vs. low) measure of the participation rate. Note that the range of state net coverage error estimates was similar in 2010 as the previous decades.

Finally, moving to 2020 we see a dramatic change in the state percent net coverage error estimates. The state net coverage error rates generally did not move in parallel as they had done in previous decades. We also see a much larger range of estimates. The key difference in methodology is that the 2020 logistic regression models included a state covariate. This reduced the synthetic bias and allowed for state-specific effects, though it may have added variability. Other differences in the census operations and cultural changes between 2010 and 2020 could also have impacted the state percent net coverage error estimates.

The change in methodology for 2020 is clearly evident in the estimate for DC, shown as the red line in Figure 1. From 1990 to 2010, DC was the state with the lowest point estimate for the net coverage error, indicating undercounts. DC is consistently the bottom line in Figure 1 from 1990 to 2010. DC had the highest percent Black or African American population of all states in the 2010 Census (Rastogi *et al.*, 2021) and had the highest percent renter-occupied housing in the 2010 Census (Mazur and Wilson 2011). These two groups were undercounted at the national level in each census from 1990 to 2020. Because the state net coverage error estimates for the 1990, 2000, and 2010 post-enumeration surveys were synthetic, the estimate for DC reflected these national-level coverage patterns. With the inclusion of a state covariate in 2020, the estimate for DC was an overcount of 4.59 percent, even though the Black percent in DC in 2020 was the highest in the U.S. (U.S. Census Bureau 2021). The state effect for DC clearly dominated the national-level race and tenure effects, which continued to show undercounts for the renter and Black or African American populations in the 2020 Census.

Figure 2 shows the synthetic and direct estimates of 2010 Census percent net coverage error by state. In 2010, only the synthetic state-level coverage estimates were reported; however, all states had enough sample to support direct estimates as well. The direct estimates were used in estimating bias and mean squared error of estimates, but were not included in any coverage reports.

Figure 2: Synthetic and Direct Estimates of Percent Net Coverage Error of 2010 Census by State

As expected, the state-level synthetic estimates are spread out less than the direct estimates. In general, the synthetic estimates are pulled toward the national average, although there are exceptions. For DC, depicted by the red line in Figure 2, the direct estimate was closer to the national average than the synthetic estimate. So, even though the synthetic estimator generally pulled estimates to the national mean, this did not mean the synthetic estimate for all states were closer to the national average than the direct estimate.

We generally saw agreement in the direction of the percent net coverage error, even though the magnitude of the errors was generally smaller for the synthetic estimates. However, there were also exceptions to this. For some state, the sign of the synthetic estimate was different from the sign of the direct estimate.

In summary, synthetic estimates of percent net coverage error can differ from state-specific direct estimates. When the estimation method changed from a synthetic estimator to an IBC model estimator in 2020, state-level percent net coverage errors had a wider range and the relative ordering changed as well. Of course, other changes in society and census operations could also explain some of these changes. When isolating the estimates to the 2010 post-enumeration survey and census, we confirmed that state-level synthetic estimates differed from direct estimates in terms of their sign, magnitude, and relative order. As mentioned in Hill (2022), the change in estimation approach from biased synthetic estimations in 1990, 2000, and 2010 to IBC model estimators confounds comparisons of percent net coverage error between 2010 and 2020.

4.2 Relative Root Mean Squared Error (RRMSE)

The root mean squared error is defined as the square root of the variance plus the squared bias. For direct estimators and IBC model estimators, there is no synthetic bias, so the root mean squared error is equivalent to the standard error. However, because synthetic estimators are biased, the mean squared error includes a nonzero bias term which should be estimated.

The methodology for estimating mean squared errors of the state estimates changed over the years. The 1990 and 2000 state estimates included synthetic bias, but this bias was neither estimated nor reported. The uncertainty estimates for these years were based on sampling variance alone. Thus, the uncertainty measures for the state estimates in these decades were quite small. Davis and Mulligan (2012) show that all 2000 PES state estimates of percent net coverage error had standard errors below 1 percent – and most were below 0.5 percent. In 2010, the synthetic bias for states was estimated and included in the reported root mean squared errors. Thus the 2010 mean squared errors for the states were larger than in 2000. For 2020 we only reported the sampling variability because we used an IBC model estimator without synthetic bias.

Figure 3 shows the root mean squared error of the percent net coverage error. Each line represents a state. Assuming the root mean squared error is measured appropriately, being close to the 0 line is desirable because that indicates low sampling error and low synthetic bias.

Figure 3: Root Mean Squared Error of Percent Net Coverage Error by State, 2000 to 2020

Note: In 2000, synthetic bias was not quantified, so estimates of root mean squared error for 2000 underestimate the true uncertainty of the synthetic estimator.

In 2000, the PES produced synthetic point estimates, but did not estimate a bias term when estimating the root mean squared error of the state-level net coverage errors. This explains why the measures of sampling error in 2000 were so much lower than other years. In 2010, new methods were used to estimate the bias of synthetic state-level estimates. These estimates of bias were added to the variance to estimate mean squared error. In 2020, state-level coverage models included state effects which eliminated the synthetic bias for state estimates. For some states, but not all, the root mean squared error was larger in 2020 than in 2010.

While the 2020 state percent net coverage error estimates do not have synthetic bias, the trade-off is that some states have large standard errors. DC is one such example. The DC overcount of 4.59 percent was not statistically significantly different from zero because there was a large standard error of 4.93 percent. Some other states with large point estimates in 2020 had high standard errors as well. For example, the net coverage error was not statistically significantly different from zero for Montana (-4.39 percent, standard error 3.70 percent) and Nevada (4.42 percent, standard error 3.44 percent). The sampling errors of the 2020 state estimates are partly explained by state sample sizes. We see that small states tend to have larger standard errors because of their smaller samples.

Table 1 illustrates the impact of changes to estimating mean squared error for DC. The sampling error of the synthetic 2000 estimate was only 0.36 percent. When synthetic bias was estimated in 2010, the root mean squared error estimate grew to 2.20. We note that the sample size of the 2010 PES was smaller than the 2000 PES, so part of this increase in the uncertainty estimate may be because of an increase in sampling error, but we suspect that the majority of the increase is because of the inclusion of the estimate of the synthetic bias. In 2020, the estimated sampling error for DC was 4.93 percent.

Year	Uncertainty Estimate Description	Uncertainty Estimate
2000	Sampling error from synthetic estimator	0.36
2010	Root mean squared error including estimate of synthetic bias	2.20
2020	Sampling error from model without synthetic bias	4.93

Table 1: Uncertainty Estimates for the District of Columbia in Recent Post-Enumeration Surveys

Assuming all else is equal, it seems that the synthetic estimates in 2010 generally had lower root mean squared error than the IBC model estimates in 2020.

To further investigate how synthetic bias impacted estimates of uncertainty, we analyzed the contribution of synthetic bias to mean squared error estimates and also compared the mean squared error estimates to the variance of the direct estimates in 2010.

Figure 4 shows a decomposition of the estimated mean squared error of the state-level synthetic estimates of net coverage error from 2010. The ends of the bars show the estimated mean squared error of the published synthetic estimate. The mean squared error of the synthetic estimate is broken into two parts. The teal portion shows the variance component. The bias squared term is shown in pink. Together the variance and the bias of the synthetic estimate sum to the mean squared error. The black dot shows the mean squared error of the direct estimate.

Figure 4: Decomposition of Estimated Mean Squared Error and Sampling Variance of Net Coverage Error Rates of 2010 Census

In the upper right of Figure 4, we see the 12 states where the mean squared error of the synthetic estimate was less than the mean squared error of the direct estimator. This is what most statisticians would expect. Although biased, the synthetic estimate has lower mean squared error than the mean squared error of the unbiased direct estimate.

However, in 37 states the estimated mean squared error of the direct estimator was less than the estimated mean squared error of the synthetic estimate. So, in most states, we estimated that the direct estimator had less uncertainty than the synthetic estimate.

The bias term shown in pink is quite large. In fact, the estimated synthetic bias term was generally greater than the variance term for the synthetic estimator. It looks as if we might have overestimated synthetic bias. We made a lot of strong assumptions when estimating bias. Indeed, estimating the bias of synthetic estimates is difficult, rarely done, and requires strong assumptions. However, not estimating bias would be rather problematic and overstate our confidence in the estimates.

Synthetic estimation is often used to reduce the root mean squared error of direct estimates. However, for most states, the estimated root mean squared error of the synthetic estimate was greater than the estimated root mean squared error of the direct estimate. Estimates of squared synthetic bias were larger than estimates of variance, indicating that either estimates of bias were inflated or point estimates could differ substantially from true values. The fact that that estimation of synthetic bias requires strong assumptions and the evaluation of synthetic bias requires some high-quality data about the true population makes it hard to discern whether estimates of bias were inflated or accurate. The estimation of mean squared error is important because it has ramifications on statistical tests.

4.3 Statistical Tests

Statistical tests are often performed to detect if differences in the data are the result of random chance from sampling or an actual effect in the population. Estimates of root mean squared error are used to form confidence intervals and test for statistically significant differences. However, for the 2010 post-enumeration survey, the combination of using an estimator that attenuated the magnitude of state-level percent net coverage errors and of conservatively estimating synthetic bias decreased the ability to detect statistically significant results.

In 2010, the Census Bureau used the root mean squared errors to test if state-level coverage rates were statistically different from zero. A 90% significant level was used – meaning that on average, one out of every 10 tests would show up as statistically significant when there really wasn't a difference. Under the null hypothesis (where all states would have 0 net coverage error) with a 90% confidence interval, we would have expected five states to have a statistically significant undercount or overcount by chance (10 percent of 50 states). However, in 2010, no states were found to have a statistically significant net coverage error rate that was different from 0 using the root mean squared errors. This further suggests that a) the published root mean squared errors from 2010 were excessively large, b) the synthetic state-level estimates were highly biased (in the direction toward the national coverage error rate), or c) both.

To explore how the estimation strategy employed for the 2010 PES may have impacted tests of statistical significance, we computed tests of significance using direct state-level point estimates and estimates of their sampling error. Note that these direct estimates were not reported in 2010. Figure 5 shows the 90% confidence interval of the direct estimates of percent net coverage error using their estimated sampling errors for the seven states that showed a statistically significant result. The states names were suppressed in this graph, but six states would have had a statistically significant overcount in 2010 had we produced direct estimates and one state would have had a statistically significant undercount in 2010.

Figure 5: Confidence Intervals of 2010 Direct Net Coverage Error Estimates using Standard Error

Altogether, had we produced state-level direct estimates of percent net coverage error and estimated their standard errors, we would have had seven states that had a statistically significant percent net coverage error that was different from 0. In 2010, none of the synthetic state-level estimates showed a statistically significant percent net coverage error when using the root mean squared errors.

Although synthetic estimation has some advantages and is very appropriate in some circumstances, it may have prevented us from detecting states with coverage errors in 2010. Had we reported direct estimates, we likely would have identified some states with statistically significant coverage errors.

In conclusion, reporting of statistically significant results is sensitive to how points and uncertainty are measured. Caution should be exercised when using the PES to draw conclusions in state-level coverage trends between the 2010 and 2020 censuses because the 2010 coverage estimates contained synthetic bias, and the 2020 estimates did not have synthetic bias.

5. Discussion

Leading up to 2020, we could have put more effort into improving the way to estimate synthetic bias or shifted to a direct or IBC model estimator. We decided to remove the synthetic bias by using an IBC model estimator. As a consequence, caution should be exercised when comparing percent net coverage error rates between 2020 and previous years. The inclusion of one variable, state, in the dual-system estimation models certainly contributed to the greater spread and change in the distribution of coverage estimates in 2020 compared to prior decades. Despite this increase in variability, the IBC model estimator improved our ability to detect states with coverage errors and to accurately portray the quality of the census in each state.

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